

Effects of Set Size and Plant Population Density on the Yield Attributes, Yield and Quality of Onion (*Allium Cepa L.*)

M. A. Khan¹, M. M. Rahman^{2*}, S. Rinky³

¹ Senior Scientific Officer(Horticulture), Spices Research Sub-Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Faridpur, Bangladesh

² Scientific Officer (Horticulture), Spices Research Sub-Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Faridpur, Bangladesh

³ College of Agricultural Sciences, IUBAT-International University of Business Agriculture and Technology Dhaka-1230

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*Corresponding Author:
Md. Mustiqur Rahman

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Plant population and set bulb size for onion production in set method (bulb to bulb) is very important issues for early onion production. The present study was designed to overcome this issue and was conducted with the variety BARI Piaz-1 in randomized complete block design with three replications and two factors, i) plant population densities: P₁. 100 plants/m², P₂. 66 plants/m² and P₃. 44 plants/m²; and ii) onion set sizes: S₁. <1.5g, S₂. 2±0.5g, S₃. 4±0.5g, S₄. 6±0.5g and S₅. 8±0.5g). The plant population density, set size and their combined effects had significant on the characters studied except only days to 50% plant emergence for plant density. The highest incidence of bolting (19.09%), incidence of multiplier bulb (42.50%), bulb diameter (3.64cm) and bulb weight (26.66g) were recorded from lower plant density (P₃) but the treatment P₃ showed the lowest TSS content (19.76 °brix), bulb dry matter content (18.09g) and yield (13.48t/ha). The highest plant density (P₁) gave the maximum TSS content (21.74 °brix), bulb dry matter (19.36%) and yield (18.96 t/ha). The largest set size (S₅) produced the maximum incidence of bolting (22.68%), incidence of multiplier bulb (45.45%), bulb diameter (3.71cm), bulb weight (26.57g) & yield (19.09t/ha) but the minimum TSS content (20.09 °brix). However, the lowest incidence of bolting (3.43%), incidence of multiplier bulb (22.21%), bulb diameter (2.73cm), bulb weight (19.46g) & yield (13.41t/ha) were observed in the smallest set size (S₁). The combined effect of P₃S₅ registered the highest incidence of bolting (30.07%), incidence of multiplier bulb (61.80%), bulb diameter (4.16cm) & bulb weight (31.22g) and the lowest TSS content (19.20 °brix) & bulb dry matter content (17.36%). The combined effect of P₁S₁ demonstrated the minimum incidence of bolting (1.93%), incidence of multiplier bulb (11.40%), bulb diameter (2.46cm) & bulb weight (17.49g) and the maximum TSS content (22.62 °brix) & bulb dry matter content (20.33%). However, the maximum (20.64t/ha) and minimum (10.24t/ha) yield were recorded from the combination of P₁S₁ and P₃S₁, respectively. In

conclusion, moderate plant population density along with medium set size (from 4±0.5g to 6±0.5g) would be the suitable options for growing early onion crops through set planting (bulb to bulb) method.

Keywords: SET SIZE, SET METHOD, PLANT POPULATION, BULB TO BULB, YIELD, QUALITY.

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.), central Asian in origin, is a high valued popular spice-cum-bulbous biennial vegetable crop in the world (Rabinowitch and Brewster, 1990). It is commonly known as “Queen of the kitchen” due to its highly valued flavor, aroma, unique tested and the medicinal properties of its flavor compounds (Griffiths *et al.*, 2002). Onion is cultivated for more than 4000 years but the earliest record comes from Egypt (The Holy Qur’an: chapter no. 2 - Surah Al-Baqarah and verse no. 61). The major onion producers are China, India, USA, Turkey, Korea, Japan, Spain, Egypt, Holland, Pakistan, Israel, Syria and Ukraine. In Bangladesh, onion is widely grown in the greater districts of Faridpur, Pabna, Rangpur, Rajshahi, Dinajpur, Dhaka, Mymensingh, Manikgonj, Kushtia, Bogura, Cumilla and Barihsal. Among the spice crops, onion stands first place in Bangladesh based on the daily intake (35g/day/person) and production as well (Khan *et al.*, 2020). Onion is produced 19.51 lakh metric tonnes per annum and the yield is very low, being 9.71 t/ha (BBS, 2020) in the country as compared to Indian onion yield, being 16.10 t/ha (Ratan *et al.*, 2017). The production of the country does not fulfill the country’s demand. Storage loss of rabi (winter) onion is around 30-40% which is estimated at nearly 5-6 lakh metric tonnes onions per year (Khan *et al.*, 2020). The government of Bangladesh imports around 10 lakh metric tonnes onions per year expending foreign money for meeting the demand of the country (Khan *et al.*, 2020). So, onion farmers in the country should produce onion round the year applying different growing methods. Farmers in Bangladesh grow their onion following three methods: a) transplanting of seedlings, b) direct seeding in line or broadcast and set (bulb to bulb) method. Around 60-65% and 5-10% of total annual onion are produced using transplanting of seedlings and direct seeding, respectively while the rest by onion set (Rahim *et al.*, 1992). Planned to use sets for direct planting of onion and to eliminate the step of nursery raising which is not only time consuming but laborious as well. In many countries, onions are largely planted as sets (Khokhar *et al.*, 2002). Set planting is followed for growing only green onions but not for store purpose. For getting early crop, the sets (small bulbs) are used for planting which are produced in previous season by seeding thickly. True seeds of onion @ 8-10 g m² are sown on raised or flat beds. The best time for sowing of seeds for getting quality sets is November. All other cultural operations in raising of sets are similar to that of nursery for transplanting. The plants are left in the nursery bed till there is top fall. Harvesting is done along with tops. Bulbs are stored in a well-ventilated room. The crops grown by set method come into the market quite early in the season and meets market demand for several months. However, early harvesting during the season compensates by high price received for the crops. The bulbs produced in this method are entirely fresh (green onion) and these bulbs are immediately consumed. The use of sets in onion production is particularly useful for extending the availability of the commodity throughout the season (Ansari, 2007). The

growth, yield and quality of onion bulb are influenced by different factors. Among them, plant population density (plant spacing) and onion set are the more important limiting factors. Size of sets and spacing has positive correlation with growth, yield and quality of onion crop (Rahim *et al.*, 1992). The widest plant spacing produce the maximum leaves per plant, plant height, bulb weight but it reduced the yield/ha (Jilani *et al.*, 2010; Khan *et al.*, 2002 and Khan *et al.*, 2003). They further stated that the closest plant spacing produced significantly maximum yield per hectare. Mondal and Alam (2003) stated that larger bulb gave the maximum diameter of bulb, bulb weight and bulb yield. The maximum incidence of multiplier bulb was recorded from larger bulbs as compared to smaller ones (Khokhar *et al.*, 2002). In Bangladesh, farmers grow their onion by planting sets following different plant density and different size of sets. Khan *et al.* (2005) opined that onion bulb production using larger sets needed a very high seed rate and became uneconomical. So far, no finding of plant population density was found earlier for onion production bulb through set method. From economic point of view, Khan *et al.* (2005) stated that the medium set size ($4 \pm 0.5\text{g}$) was suitable among the three sizes of sets ($3 \pm 0.5\text{g}$, $4 \pm 0.5\text{g}$ & $5 \pm 0.5\text{g}$). So far, no investigation was conducted on combined effect of plant density and set size for growing onion in set method.

The present experiment was, therefore, undertaken using onion variety BARI Piaz-1 for following objectives:

1. To search optimum plant population densities (plant spacing) for obtaining higher yield and quality of onion through set planting method (bulb to bulb).
2. To find out suitable set size/s for getting higher yield and quality of onion through set planting method.

Materials and methods

The experiment was conducted at Spices Research Sub-Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Faridpur, Bangladesh during winter season of 2020-2021 to find out optimum plant population density and suitable set size/s for getting higher yield and quality of onion (cv. BARI Piaz-1) bulb through set planting (bulb to bulb) method. The uniform and healthy sets were planted on 15 October 2020 adopting five sizes of set (S₁. 1.5g, S₂. $2 \pm 0.5\text{g}$, S₃. $4 \pm 0.5\text{g}$, S₄. $6 \pm 0.5\text{g}$ and S₅. $8 \pm 0.5\text{g}$) in the experimental plots maintaining three plant population densities: P₁. 100 plants/m² (10 cm x 10 cm), P₂. 66 plants/m² (15 cm x 10 cm) and P₃. 44 plants/m² (15 cm x 15 cm). Hence, the treatment combination was 15 (P₁S₁, P₁S₂, P₁S₃, P₁S₄, P₁S₅, P₂S₁, P₂S₂, P₂S₃, P₂S₄, P₂S₅, P₃S₁, P₃S₂, P₃S₃, P₃S₄ and P₃S₅). The experimental site is belonging to Agro Ecological Zone (AEZ) no. 12 (Low Ganges River Floodplain). The geographic coordinates of the trial site are 23° 11' N and 89° 09' E. The elevation of Faridpur is about 12 meters above sea level. The soil analysis data of the experimental field (Table 1) demonstrated that the trial ground was texturally clay loam with the pH values of the soil were 7.30. While the organic matter was 1.84%. These sets were grown at SRSC, Faridpur in previous season (2019-2020) by seeding thickly. True seeds of onion @ 8-10 g m² were sown on raised or flat beds for getting the sets. The trial was set up in randomized complete block design with three replications. The unit plot size was 3 m x 2 m. The experimental field was fertilized with 5 tones well-decomposed cowdung, 120 kg N, 50 kg P, 85 kg K and 40 kg S per hectare. Nitrogen, phosphate, potash and sulphur were supplied in the form

of Urea, TSP, MP and Gypsum, respectively. The entire quantity of cowdung, P, K, S and one third of N were applied as basal dose during land preparation. The remaining N was used as top dress in two equal splits at 20 and 30 days after set planting. The fungicide mancozeb/iprodione @ 3 g/l litre of water was sprayed at fortnightly interval commencing from one month after set planting. All other recommended management practices were followed for each accession and variety. The data were recorded on: days to 50% plant emergence, plant height (cm), number of leaves per plant (no.), percent bolting (%), diameter of bulb (cm), individual bulb weight (g), percent multiplier (split) bulbs (%), dry matter content of bulbs (%), total soluble solid content (°brix), bulbs weight per plot (kg/ha) then calculated as yield per hectare (t). Ten plants were randomly selected from each plot for data recording and averaging it. Days to 50% plant emergence was recorded for each replication from days after set planting. Later average days to 50% plant emergence were determined. Plant height and number of leaves were recorded at 45 and 65 days after planting of sets. But average plant height and number of leaves were presented in the paper. The number of bolting (flowering stalk) plants was visually counted in each plot, recorded and expressed in percent in relation to the total number of plants. Bulbs were harvested at maturity when the pseudostem becomes flaccid and unable to support the leaf blades (Brewster, 1990^a) on January 12, 2021. The leaves of harvested onion were removed by cutting 8-10 cm above the bulb (Brewster, 1990^b). The leaves of harvested onion were removed at seven days after curing by cutting 8-10 cm above the bulb (Brewster, 1990^b). After curing, the total bulb fresh weight was measured for each plot. Bulb diameter (equatorial) is the maximum width of the onion in plane perpendicular to the polar diameter. The number of multiplier bulbs was visually counted in each plot, recorded and expressed in percent in relation to the total number of bulbs per plot. The percent dry matter content of bulbs was calculated by dry weight basis as per procedure of Walle *et al.* (2018). The total soluble solids (TSS) content of bulbs were recorded by hand refractometer (ATAGO, Master-53M, Japan) with a range of 0-53 °brix. The recorded data were analyzed statistically as suggested by Gomez and Gomez (1984) and the means were compared by the least significant difference (LSD) for single effects but and the means were compared by the Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT) for the combined effect.

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of initial soil at the experimental plot of SRSC, BARI, Faridpur in 2020-2021 (SRDI, 2020)

Soil texture	Soil pH	OM (%)	K	Ca	Mg	Total N (%)	P	S	B	Zn	Fe	Cu	Mn
			meq/100 g				µg/g soil						
Clay loam	7.30	1.84	0.35	10.85	2.61	0.9	14.4	12.9	0.50	2.51	32.9	2.95	13.78
Critical level			0.12	2.0	0.5	0.12	7.0	10.0	0.2	0.6	4.0	0.2	1.0

Results and Discussion

Effects of plant population density

Plant growth: The plant population density (plant spacing) affected plant height, number of leaves and

percentage of bolting significantly accept days to 50% plant emergence from onion set (small bulb) for plant growth in growing onion through onion sets (bulb to bulb) method (Table 2). The highest 50% emergence of onion set (16.14 days) was recorded from the minimum plant population density (P₃. 44 plants/m² at the spacing of 15 cm x 15 cm) which was statistically similar to the value 16.07 days and 16.12 days observed from the moderate (P₂. 66 plants/m² at the spacing of 15 cm x 10 cm) and the maximum (P₁. 100 plants/m² at the spacing of 10 cm x 10 cm), respectively. The tallest plant height (53.02 cm) was obtained with the treatment P₃ which was statistically followed by the treatment P₂ (49.55 cm). While the shortest plant height (45.00 cm) was noted from the P₁ which was also statistically differed with the P₂. The increase in plant height from the minimum density might be due to more availability of nutrients, water, light and space. The results support the earlier findings of Khan and Ahmed (2013) and Singh and Singh (2003). They opined that plants with wider spacing exhibited maximum growth and development due to better nutrition by the plants. The number of leaves per plant was increased with the decrease in plan density from 5.61 to 8.45 with the more number of leaves from the treatment P₃. However, the lowest number of leaves (5.61) was found with the treatment P₁. The three mean values of the treatments were statistically different with each other. That variation was also due to the reasons mentioned above in the case of plant height. The results showed the similar pattern for the percentage of bolting (growing flower stalk in onion plant) as was in plant height. The maximum bolting incidence (17.57%) was counted from the P₃ which was followed by the P₂ (12.99%). The treatment P₁ had the minimum bolting incidence (8.00%). Attallah and El-Abedin (2012) and Hassan (2006) also found a large percent of bolting incidence from lower density of plants. On the contrary, Ansari *et al.* (2000) found no effects of plant density on bolting incidence. The bolter bulb (the bulb with growing the flower stalk) bears hard center which reduces the quality and the market value of that bulb as well (Khan *et al.*, 2020).

Table 2. Effects of plant population on the growth, yield and quality of green onion at Spices Research Sub-Centre, Faridpur during 2020-2021

Plant population density	50% plant emergence (days)	Plant height (cm)	No. leaves/plant (no.)	Bolting (%)	Multiplier bulb (%)	Bulb diameter (cm)	Individual bulb weight (g)	TSS (°brix)	Bulb dry matter (%)	Yield (t/ha)
P ₁ :100 plants/m ²	16.12a	45.00c	5.61c	8.00c	17.59c	2.80c	18.60c	21.74a	19.36a	18.96a
P ₂ :66 plants/m ²	16.07a	49.55b	7.26b	12.99b	35.85b	3.29b	24.56b	21.09ab	18.51b	16.26b
P ₃ : 44 plants/m ²	16.14a	53.02a	8.45a	17.57a	42.50a	3.64a	26.66a	19.76b	18.09c	13.48c
CV(%)	8.78	11.15	9.61	19.09	10.25	7.82	6.94	4.99	6.87	12.25
Level of significance	NS	**	**	**	**	**	**	*	**	**

Foot note: TSS: Total soluble solid content ** Significant at the 1% level of significance, * Significant at the 5% level of significance and NS. Not significant. Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Table 3. Effects of set size on the growth, yield and quality of green onion at Spices Research Sub-Centre, Faridpur during 2020-2021

Set size of onion	50% plant emergence (days)	Plant height (cm)	No. leaves/plant (no.)	Bolting (%)	Multiplier bulb (%)	Bulb diameter (cm)	Individual bulb weight (g)	TSS (°brix)	Bulb dry matter (%)	Yield (t/ha)
S ₁ : <1.5g	18.24a	43.96e	6.59c	3.43d	22.21d	2.73d	19.46d	21.50a	19.54a	13.41d
S ₂ : 2±0.5g	16.59b	46.38d	6.94bc	6.17d	25.73d	2.83c	21.61c	21.30a	19.04b	14.70c
S ₃ : 4±0.5g	16.27b	49.07c	7.10b	13.94c	30.44c	3.34c	23.96b	20.85b	18.53c	16.42b
S ₄ : 6±0.5g	15.06c	51.91b	7.25b	18.04b	36.08b	3.59b	25.41ab	20.56b	18.21d	17.96ab
S ₅ : 8±0.5g	14.41d	54.63a	7.68a	22.68a	45.45a	3.71a	26.57a	20.09c	17.95e	19.09a
CV(%)	8.78	11.15	9.61	19.09	10.25	7.82	6.94	4.99	6.87	12.25
Level of significance	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	*	**	**

Foot note: ** Significant at the 1% level of significance, * Significant at the 5% level of significance and TSS: Total soluble solid content. Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Bulb development: The data in the Table 2 demonstrated that different plant population density showed significant influence on the parameters of bulb development such as diameter of bulb, individual bulb weight. The diameter of bulb was increased with the decrease in plant density ranged from 2.80 to 3.64 cm. The bigger size of bulb (3.64 cm) was recorded from the treatment P₃ followed (3.29 cm) by the moderate density (P₂). Nevertheless, the treatment P₁ showed the smaller size of bulb (2.80 cm). The increase in bulb size from lower plant population density might be attributed to the space, nutrition, light, water available per plant (Das, 1992). Similar findings were also published by Attallah and El-Abedin (2012), Muhammad et al. (2011), Darwar et al. (2007) and Singh et al. (1998). An increase in plant density resulted in reduction of bulb diameter (Muhammad et al., 2011). Darwar et al. (2007) stated that higher plant density resulted in smaller bulb size. Wider spacing (lower plant population density) gave the maximum diameter of bulb in comparison of closer plant spacing (higher plant population density), as described by Singh et al. (1998). Leskovar et al. (2012) also found similar observation as increasing plant density reduced the average bulb size. The similar pattern of the result for individual bulb weight was observed as was in diameter of bulb ranged from 18.60 to 26.66 g. The maximum individual bulb weight (26.66 g) was registered with the treatment P₃ and the minimum (18.60 g) was recorded from the treatment P₁. However, the treatment P₂ demonstrated the moderate weight (24.56 g) of individual bulb. These three mean values were statistically different with each other. The superiority of individual plant from lower plant population density is for utilization more soil water, space, nutrition, air and light which help the bulb to get up better growth and thereafter heavier fresh weight of bulb from lower plant density in comparison of higher plant density (Attallah and El-Abedin, 2012 and Das, 1992). The results are also consistent with findings of Khan and Ahmed (2013) and Farooq *et al.* (1990).

Yield and quality of bulb: The variation in yield and quality traits of onion bulb such as percent of multiplier bulb, total soluble solid (TSS) content and dry matter content of bulb for three plant density treatments was statistically significant (Table 2). The yield pattern was reverse with the pattern of individual bulb weight. The bulb yield was increased with the increase in plant population density from 13.48 to 18.96 t/ha with maximum yield (18.96 t/ha) in P₁ followed by P₂ (16.26 t/ha). And the minimum yield (13.48 t/ha) was found from the treatment P₃. The three values of plant density treatment were statistically different with each other. Higher bulb yield per unit area was associated with closer plant spacing (higher plant density) due to accommodation of maximum number of plants. The results corroborate with the findings of Muhammad *et al.* (2011) and Singh *et al.* (1998). Attallah and El-Abedin (2012) and Leskovar *et al.* (2012) also found similar observation as increasing plant density reduced the average bulb size but it increased the yield. In the study, about 10,00,000; over 6,60,000 and over 4,40,000 plants were estimated in one hectare of land as per treatment P₁, P₂ and P₃, respectively for growing onion through set method. As per plant density treatment, the P₁ needs nearly 1.50 and 2.50 times more onion sets/ha than those of P₂ and P₃ treatment, respectively. In the present study, the fertilizer doses were similar for every plant density treatment. The bulb size or individual bulb weight may be increased by applying more nutrition in respect of the treatment P₁. The maximum multiplier bulb (42.50%) was noted in P₃ which was statistically followed by the P₂ (35.85%). The minimum value (17.59%) was estimated from the

P₁ which was also significant difference with P₂. The present report support the observation made by Attallah and El-Abedin (2012) and Hassan (2006) who stated that percent of split bulb (multiplier bulb) decreased with the increase in plan density. The total soluble solid content (TSS) was decreased with the decrease in plant density ranged from 21.74 to 19.76 °brix with the maximum TSS (21.74 °brix) from P₁ insignificantly followed (21.09 °brix) by P₂. The P₃ showed the minimum TSS (19.76 °brix) which was significantly differed with P₁ but was identical to the P₂. According to Rajkumar (1997), low TSS content implies high percent of water in onion contributing to larger bulbs. Singh and Singh (2003) also registered the similar finding as larger bulb contains maximum water. However, Laskovar *et al.* (2012) found no significant influence on the TSS content among plant density treatments. The maximum plant density (P₁) gave the highest dry matter content of bulb (19.36%) insignificantly followed (18.51%) by moderate plant density (P₂). Nonetheless, the minimum plant density (P₃) had the lowest dry matter content (18.09%). The present result is in line with finding of Singh and Singh (2003). On the contrary, the result is not agrees with findings of Singh *et al.* (1998) and Das (1992). Singh *et al.* (1998) cited that in comparison of higher plant density, lower plant density gave the maximum dry weight of bulb. Das (1992) also noted that dry matter was adversely affected at high population density.

Effects of onion set size

Plant growth: Onion set sizes showed significant difference in plant growth characters such as days to 50% plant emergence, plant height, number of leaves per plant and percentage of bolting, presented in Table 3. The earliest emergence (14.41 days) was attained from the biggest set (S₅: 8 ± 0.5g) which significantly followed (15.06 days and 16.27 days) by the set sizes S₄ (6 ± 0.5g) and S₃ (4 ± 0.5g), respectively. Nevertheless, the maximum emergence (18.24 days) of onion set was recorded from the smallest set (S₁: <1.5g) significantly followed (16.59 days) by the S₂ (2 ± 0.5g). Early plant emergence from large onion set planting, may be attributed to the higher sprouted leaf initials, inner and outer rooting as well as higher food reserve in them which might have resulted in early plant emergence. This finding agrees with the finding of Khan (.2003). The largest set (S₅) produced the tallest plant (54.63 cm) which significantly followed (51.91 cm and 49.07 cm) by S₄ and S₃, respectively. On the other hand, the smallest set (S₁) gave the shortest (43.96 cm) plant significantly followed by S₂ (46.38 cm). The superiority of large sets may be explained on the basis of higher food reserve in them. This naturally gives a better start to growing plants. The current finding is similar to the result of Muktadir *et al.* (2001). They reported that significantly the highest plant height was produced from the largest size of mother bulbs. The treatment S₃ had the maximum number of leaves per plant (7.68) significantly followed (7.25 and 7.10) by S₄ and S₃, respectively. The lowest number of leaves/plant (6.59) was recorded from the treatment S₁ insignificantly followed by S₂ (6.94). The highest number of leaves/plant obtained from larger set might happen due to the similar causes as mentioned above in plant height. The finding is in line with the finding of Singh and Singh (2003). The highest bolting (flower stalk), being 22.68%, was in the S₅ significantly followed by S₄ (18.04%). The lowest bolting (3.43%) was recorded from the treatment S₁ which was identical with value (6.17%) of S₂. The superiority of large sets may be explained on the basis of higher food reserve in them. This naturally gives a better start to growing plants and may also be responsible for the

higher number of flowering stalks (bolting) per plant. The increase in bolting with the increase in set size has been reported by Khokhar *et al.* (2001) and Khokhar *et al.* (2002).

Bulb development: The results of the set sizes, Table 3, had significant effect on the traits of bulb development such as diameter of bulb and individual bulb weight. The diameter of bulb was increased with the increase of set size ranging from 2.73 to 3.71 cm. The highest diameter of bulb (3.71 cm) was obtained from the treatment S₅ significantly followed (3.59 cm and 3.34 cm) by S₄ and S₃, respectively. However, the lowest bulb diameter (2.73 cm) was registered from S₁ significantly followed by S₂ (2.83 cm). Plants with planting large set produced the greater bulb diameter. Greater bulb diameter from large set may be attributed to the higher sprouted initials, inner and outer rooting as well as higher food reserve in them which might have resulted in early plant emergence and since their early food requirement comes from the reserve stored in the bulbs (Brewster, 1994). The result is also at par with those of Khan *et al.* (2005) and Singh and Singh (2003). Similar pattern of finding was observed for individual bulb weight as was in diameter of bulb. The treatment S₅ yielded the maximum individual bulb weight (26.57g) insignificantly followed by S₄ (25.41 g) but significantly followed by S₃ (23.96 g). Whilst the treatment S₁ produced the minimum individual bulb weight (19.46 g) significantly followed by S₂ (21.61 g). This variation might happen due to same causes as mentioned above in diameter of bulb. The similar nature of result was also published by Khan *et al.* (2005).

Yield and quality of bulb: The yield and quality parameters like percent of multiplier bulb, total soluble solid (TSS) content and dry matter content of bulb varied significantly due to different set sizes (Table 3). The yield of onion increased with the increase in set size ranging from 13.41 to 19.09 t/ha. Onion grown through the largest set (S₅) produced the maximum yield (19.09 t/ha) significantly followed by S₄ (17.96 t/ha) and S₃ (16.42 t/ha). The S₄ and S₃ were statistically identical to each other. However, the smallest set (S₁) gave the lowest yield (13.41 t/ha) significantly followed by S₂ (14.70 t/ha). Higher bulb yield from larger set size might be due to higher individual bulb weight/bulb size. Khan *et al.* (2005), Singh and Singh (2003) and Khokhar *et al.* (2002) reported the similar result. The highest incidence of multiplier bulb (45.45%) was observed in the treatment S₅ significantly followed (36.08% and 30.44%) by S₄ and S₃, respectively. The lowest incidence of multiplier bulb (22.21%) was observed in the treatment S₁ significantly followed by S₂ (25.73%). The findings of previous workers (Khan *et al.*, 2005 and Khokhar *et al.* 2002) also supported the present finding. The TSS content and dry matter content decreased with the increase in set size ranging from 21.50 to 20.09 °brix and 19.54 to 17.95%, respectively. The maximum TSS content (21.50 °brix) was recorded from the treatment S₁ which was statistically similar to the value of the S₂ (21.30 °brix) but was dissimilar to the value of S₃ (20.85 °brix). The lowest TSS content (20.09 °brix) was found from the treatment S₅ significantly followed (20.56°brix and 20.85 °brix) by S₄ and S₃, respectively. Low TSS content implies high percent of water in onion contributing to larger bulbs, as noted by Singh and Singh (2003) and Rajkumar (1997). The result of bulb dry matter content was also more or less identical to the result of TSS content with the highest dry matter content from S₁ (19.54%). The second (19.04%) and third highest (18.53%) dry matter content were recorded from S₂ and S₃ which were varied significantly with each other. The lowest dry matter content (17.95%) was registered at the S₅ significantly

followed by S₄ (18.21%). The superiority of smaller bulb for higher diameter content may be explained on the basis of lower water content in smaller bulb. Such finding is in conformity with the reports of Singh and Singh (2003).

Combined effects of plant population density and onion set size

Plant growth: The combined effects of plant population density and onion set size were found to be significant on the plant growth characters, showed in the Table 4. The earlier plant emergence (14.33%) was observed from the combination treatment P₃S₅ (lowest plant density x largest onion set) insignificantly followed by the combination of P₂S₅ (14.45%) and P₁S₅ (14.45%). The delayed emergence was recorded from P₁S₁ insignificantly followed by P₃S₁ (18.26%) and P₂S₁ (18.08%). The treatment combination P₃S₅ showed the tallest plant (58.22 cm), maximum bolting incidence (30.07%) and the highest number of leaves/plant (9.01) while the treatment combination P₁S₁ gave the shortest plant (40.20 cm), minimum bolting incidence (1.93%) and the lowest number of leaves/plant (5.07). The present results concur with the finding of Singh and Singh (2003).

Table 4. Combined effects of plant population density and set size on the growth, yield and quality of green onion at Spices Research Sub-Centre, Faridpur during 2020-2021

Plant population density x set size of onion	50% plant emergence (days)	Plant height (cm)	No. leaves/plant (no.)	Bolting (%)	Multiplier bulb (%)	Bulb diameter (cm)	Individual bulb weight (g)	TSS (°brix)	Bulb dry matter (%)	Yield (t/ha)
P ₁ S ₁	18.37a	40.20h	5.07h	1.93i	11.40i	2.46h	17.49l	22.62a	20.33a	17.22d
P ₁ S ₂	16.66bc	43.00g	5.43g	3.95gh	13.56i	2.55g	18.07kl	22.38a	19.65b	18.11c
P ₁ S ₃	16.14c-e	44.55g	5.54g	8.65f	17.84h	2.80f	18.68jk	21.66a	19.21c	19.06b
P ₁ S ₄	15.00d-f	47.00f	5.66g	11.36e	20.00h	3.01de	19.18ij	21.40b	18.97d	19.82a
P ₁ S ₅	14.45f	50.24d	6.34f	14.09d	25.15g	3.19d	19.59hi	20.61c	18.66f	20.64a
P ₂ S ₁	18.08ab	44.12g	6.84e	2.86hi	25.75g	2.73f	18.78j	21.58b	19.36c	12.76h
P ₂ S ₂	16.43cd	46.88f	7.07de	5.61g	28.98f	2.80f	22.12g	21.43b	18.87ef	13.78g
P ₂ S ₃	16.10c-e	49.00de	7.26d	14.65d	35.55de	3.43bc	25.82e	21.19b	18.41g	16.74d
P ₂ S ₄	15.29c-f	52.30c	7.52d	17.95c	39.58c	3.67c	27.17d	20.80c	18.05h	18.34c
P ₂ S ₅	14.45f	55.44b	7.70c	23.87b	49.40b	3.79b	28.91c	20.46c	17.84hi	19.66b
P ₃ S ₁	18.26a	47.55ef	7.86c	5.49g	29.48f	3.00de	22.11g	20.31c	18.92ef	10.24i
P ₃ S ₂	16.67bc	49.25d	8.33b	8.96f	34.65e	3.14	24.63f	20.09d	18.59g	12.21h
P ₃ S ₃	16.56c	53.66c	8.49b	18.52c	37.94cd	3.80b	27.37d	19.71d	17.97h	13.46f
P ₃ S ₄	14.90ef	56.44b	8.56b	24.82b	48.65b	4.08a	29.89b	19.49d	17.61ji	14.89e
P ₃ S ₅	14.33f	58.22a	9.01a	30.07a	61.80a	4.16a	31.22a	19.20d	17.36i	16.96d
CV(%)	8.78	11.15	9.61	19.09	10.25	7.82	6.94	4.99	6.87	12.25
Level of significance	*	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

Foot note: P₁:100 plants/m², P₂:66 plants/m², P₃: 44 plants/m², S₁:<1.5g, S₂:2±0.5g, S₃:4±0.5g, S₄:6±0.5g, S₅:8±0.5g, TSS: Total soluble solid content, ** Significant at the 1% level of significance and * Significant at the 5% level of significance . Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

They stated that the maximum number of leaves was found with combination of larger set size and wider planting distance compared to all treatments combinations (Singh and Singh, 2003).

Bulb development: The combined effects of plant population density and onion set size showed a wide range of variation on the bulb development traits studied (Table 4). The treatment combination P₃S₅ had the diameter of bulb (4.16 cm) and individual bulb weight (31.22 g). The bulb diameter was insignificantly followed by the treatment combination P₃S₄ (4.08 cm) but the individual bulb weight was significantly followed by the treatment combination P₃S₄ (29.89 g). The lowest diameter of bulb (2.46 cm) and individual bulb weight (17.49 g) were recorded from the treatment combination P₁S₁. Singh and Singh (2003) published the identical reports with the present findings. The maximum fresh weight of bulb and bulb diameter were found with combination of larger set size and wider planting distance compared to all treatments combinations (Singh and Singh, 2003).

Yield and quality of onion: The outcome of the study depicted that there were significant variation between plant population density and onion set size in relation to the yield and characters of quality which are presented graphically: multiplier bulb total soluble solid content & dry matter of bulb (Table 4). The maximum yield (20.64 t/ha) was obtained from the treatment combination P₁S₅ (highest density x largest bulb size) which was similar to the yield (19.82 t/ha) of the combination P₁S₄. The treatment combination P₃S₁ had the lowest yield of bulb (10.24 t/ha) significantly followed by the combination P₃S₂ (12.21 t/ha) and the combination P₂S₁ (17.76 t/ha). Singh and Singh (2003) also found similar result as was found in the current study. The highest yield was observed from the combination of bigger size bulb and closer planting distance (Singh and Singh, 2003). The maximum incidence of multiplier bulb (61.80%) was registered in the treatment combination of P₃S₅ and the minimum incidence of multiplier bulb (11.40%) was noted with the combination between P₁S₁. The treatment combination P₁S₁ resulted in the highest TSS content (22.62 °brix) and dry matter of bulb (20.33%). However, the lowest TSS content (19.20 °brix) and dry matter content of bulb (17.36%) were recorded from the treatment combination of P₃S₅. The maximum juice (water) content in bulb was found with combination of larger set size and wider planting distance compared to all treatments combinations (Singh and Singh, 2003).

Conclusion

Based on the result of the present study, the following conclusions could be drawn for growing early onion crops through onion set planting (bulb to bulb) method.

- The plant population densities markedly varied in the characters studied except 50% plant emergence. Though the total bulb yield obtained from the highest plant population density (100 plants/m²) was the maximum but marketable bulb yield of those bulbs was lower due to their smaller size of bulb. On the other hand, total bulb yield was much lower in the lowest density (44 plants/m²) than other ones and quality of their bulb was also inferior as well due to maximum bolting, multiplier bulb, total soluble solid content & dry matter content. Hence, the medium plant density (66 plants/m² = 15 cm x 10 cm) performed the best results with the application of similar doses of nutrition.

- The bulb size may be increased applying higher doses of nutrition in case of highest plant population density (100 plants/m² =10 cm x 10 cm) due to lot of plant population as compared to medium (66 plants/m² =15 cm x 10 cm) and the lowest (44 plants/m² =15 cm x 15 cm) plant population density.
- The onion set size greatly influenced on the traits studied. The yield obtained from largest sets was the maximum but the quality of that bulb was poor due to inferior performance on incidence of bolting, multiplier bulb, total soluble solid content and dry matter content of bulb. Besides, the set size S₁ and S₂ performed better in respect of bolting, multiplier bulb, TSS content & dry matter content but they produced inferior individual bulb weight, diameter of bulb and yield as well. So, the set size having from 4 ± 0.5g to 6 ± 0.5g of bulbs could be selected.

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Dr. Md. Alauddin Khan

Senior Scientist of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute. He completed his PhD from Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur, Bangladesh.

Md. Musfiqur Rahman

Scientist of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute. He completed his MS degree from Bangladesh Agricultural University.

Samiazzaman Rinky

She completed her graduation from College of Agricultural Sciences, IUBAT-International University of Business Agriculture and Technology Dhaka-1230.

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